

New model for estimating trophic level in mammalian carnivores based on bone collagen individual amino acids nitrogen stable isotopes

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The sites

Our research material comes from two sites: Białowieża Primeval Forest (the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve) and Perspektywiczna Cave (the site of Late Pleistocene hyena den) (Fig. S1), both situated in Poland. The material from Białowieża Primeval Forest includes bones of modern animals (modern wolf *Canis lupus* and its prey: red deer *Cervus elaphus*, roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*, European bison *Bison bonasus*, and wild boar *Sus scrofa*), collected from dead wild animals by the Mammal Research Institute of the Polish Academy of Sciences (Białowieża, Poland) between 1969 and 2011 and stored at the institute. The prey species constituted the main part of the Białowieża wolf diet according to years-long ecological monitoring in the Białowieża forest (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000). The material from Perspektywiczna Cave includes bones of Late Pleistocene animals (spotted hyena *Crocota crocuta* and its prey: mammoth *Mammuthus primigenius*, woolly rhinoceros *Coelodonta antiquitatis*, steppe bison/auroch *Bison/Bos*, horse *Equus ferus*, and reindeer *Rangifer tarandus*), excavated between 2012-2018 and stored at the Institute of Archaeology, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun (Toruń, Poland). The importance of prey species in the hyena diet was confirmed by analysis of the hyena den's bone accumulation (Krajcarz et al., 2025).

Fig. S1. Location of the Białowieża Primeval Forest (modern wolf and its prey assemblage) and Perspektywiczna Cave sites (Late Pleistocene cave hyena and its prey assemblage).

Stable isotope standards

The 15 AAs reference standard included: Ala (Shokko Science, $43.57 \pm 0.13\text{‰}$), Val (USGS-74, 30.2‰), Gly (Shokko Science, $-25.73 \pm 0.24\text{‰}$), Leu (Shokko, $6.33 \pm 0.27\text{‰}$), Ile (Sigma Aldrich, $-1.51 \pm 0.04\text{‰}$), Nle (Sigma Aldrich, $-1.96 \pm 0.17\text{‰}$), Pro (Indiana, $-7.72 \pm 0.10\text{‰}$), Thr (Sigma Aldrich, $-0.36 \pm 0.11\text{‰}$), Asp (Shokko Science, $35.11 \pm 0.44\text{‰}$), Ser (Sigma Aldrich, $-3.43 \pm 0.09\text{‰}$), Glu (USGS-40, $-4.65 \pm 0.05\text{‰}$), Met (Sigma Aldrich, $-1.89 \pm 0.16\text{‰}$), Phe (Shokko Science, $1.81 \pm 0.04\text{‰}$), Hyp (Sigma Aldrich, -6.0‰), and Lys (Sigma Aldrich, $-0.63 \pm 0.08\text{‰}$).

AA derivatization

We followed the NAIP (N-acetyl isopropyl ester) derivatization method by Corr et al. (2007). In the esterification step, isopropanol and acetyl chloride (1 ml; 4:1, v:v) were added to the dried samples, the air was displaced by filling the tube with N_2 , and tubes were capped and sealed with TPFPE tape and heated at 100°C for 1 h. The reaction was stopped by placing the samples in the freezer at -35°C for 5 min. The sample were dried with a stream of N_2 at 40°C . To ensure full removal of the residual solvent, 1 ml of dichloromethane (DCM) was added twice during the drying process. In the acylation step, 1 ml of acetic anhydride–triethylamine–acetone mixture (1:2:5, v:v:v) was added, the tubes filled with N_2 , sealed, and heated at 60°C for 10 min. The mixture was cooled and dried at room temperature with a gentle stream of N_2 , the DCM step was repeated twice. Derivatized samples were then dissolved in 2 ml of isopropyl acetate. For separation of polar (water and water-soluble contaminations) and non-polar (AA-derivates in isopropyl acetate) phases, a saturated 1 ml of NaCl solution was added to each sample, vortexed, centrifuged, and the non-polar phase was transferred to new culture tubes. The step was repeated 3 times for each sample. The final drying step was performed on ice under a gentle stream of N_2 , with DCM added 3–4 times. Samples were dissolved in isopropyl acetate, transferred to final GC vials, and stored in a freezer at -35°C until the GC-C-IRMS measurements.

AA measurement limitations

Met, Leu, and Ile showed inconsistencies among replicates (both in standards and in samples), and leucine and isoleucine showed also poor chromatography (coelution); therefore, were discarded them from further corrections. Pro and Thr were separated, but had very close retention times. Lys did not appear in the chromatographs, possibly due to its very late retention time. For other AAs in the reference standard, the SD of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ measurements ranged within a batch from $<0.01\text{‰}$ (minimum observed for Glx) to 1.26‰ (maximum observed for Hyp), on average 0.59‰ .

Quality control

The C:N atomic ratio in studied collagen extracts was in the range 3.2–3.5 (Bocherens & Drucker, 2003; Krajcarz et al., 2023) which is within the acceptable range for uncontaminated, undegraded collagen (DeNiro, 1985).

To evaluate the quality of our $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{AA}}$ values, we monitored the offset between proline (Pro) and hydroxyproline (Hyp) values in each sample. This offset was expected to be close to 0 due to Hyp biosynthesis entirely through the *in situ* hydroxylation of Pro (Li & Wu, 2018; O'Connell & Collins, 2018; Roberts et al., 2018). In our samples, the linear regression between the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of Pro and Hyp was $R^2 = 0.9584$ (Fig. S2), with residuals average $0.19 \pm 0.48\text{‰}$ and maximum residual value of 0.88‰ . Spearman's D correlation for $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Pro}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Hyp}}$ values was: $D = 482.5$, $P(\text{uncorr.}) < 4.3 \cdot 10^{-10}$.

We also applied the mass balance equation following (Soncin et al., 2021). This is another quality control parameter that compares the bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value calculated as a weight average of individual $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{AA}}$ values measured in GC-C-IRMS with the bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value measured in EA-IRMS. We adopted the average participation of each AA in the total collagen nitrogen pool after Harrison & Katzenberg (2003). While theoretical offset should equal 0, the GC-C-IRMS analysis does not detect some AAs due to analytical issues (Hofmann et al., 2003), so the mass balance of GC-C-IRMS does not cover the entire isotopic composition of collagen. Some offset was therefore expected. According to good practice in statistics (Larsen et al., 2022), we accepted the offset in a sample that was lower than twice of the entire dataset offsets' SD.

In our samples, we reliably identified the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of 10 AAs (Ala, Val, Gly, Pro, Thr, Asx, Ser, Glx, Phe, Hyp) that include around 73.5% of the entire collagen nitrogen. We found linear regression between the EA-IRMS bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and the mass balanced bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in our samples to be $R^2 = 0.9266$ (Fig. S3), with residuals average $0.26 \pm 0.69\%$, maximum residual value of 1.39% , and no residuals outside the twice SD. Spearman's D correlation for EA-IRMS bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and the mass balanced bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values was: $D = 569.5$, $P(\text{uncorr.}) < 6.1 \cdot 10^{-10}$.

Fig. S2. Comparison of proline and hydroxyproline $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in samples. In **A**) there are samples of the Białowieża Forest mammals; in **B**) those from the Perspektywiczna Cave hyena den fossil assemblage; and in **C**) all samples from both these datasets. Dotted line marks the 1:1 proportion.

Fig. S3. Comparison of EA-IRMS-measured bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values with AAs mass balanced bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values. In **A**) there are samples of the Białowieża Forest mammals; in **B**) those from the Perspektywiczna Cave hyena den fossil assemblage; and in **C**) all samples from both these datasets.

Mean diet estimation

We followed the methodology of the isotopic composition of a mean diet calculation by (M. T. Krajcarz et al., 2018). According to this approach, the mean diet's isotopic value is the weighted average of each taxon's mean isotopic value, where the weight is the taxon's participation in the carnivore's diet. It must be noticed that in contrast to controlled laboratory studies, in our study based in natural settings the taxon's participation in the mean diet is only an approximation.

For hyena, we used data after Krajcarz et al. (2025). This data was obtained therein as each prey taxon's mean isotopic value (arithmetic mean of all $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and separately all $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values available for a given taxon in our dataset) multiplied by the proportion of each taxon in the hyena's diet. To get this proportion, the NISP (the number of identified specimens) data for each taxon was transformed into consumed biomass. We used two models (model H1 and model H2).

In model H1, the consumed biomass was calculated as the product of the i^{th} taxon's NISP and its average body mass, following the methodology by Krajcarz et al. (2025):

$$BC_i = Bm_i \cdot NISP_i \quad (\text{Eqn S1})$$

where BC_i is i^{th} taxon's consumed biomass, and Bm_i is an i^{th} taxon's average body mass in kg (after Brook & Bowman, 2004), and i is a given taxon in the diet.

In model H2, we calculated the consumed biomass according to the methodology of Ackerman et al. (1984), where the proportion of consumed biomass from variable prey taxa was corrected for the digestibility. The calculation followed the formula:

$$ABC_i = (1.98 + 0.035Bm_i)NISP_i \quad (\text{Eqn S2})$$

where ABC_i is the Ackerman et al.'s approximation of the consumed biomass of the i^{th} taxon. This second model had two weaknesses. First, it was experimentally established only for prey in the range of 2–70 kg of the body mass, while our dataset includes animals of a much larger body mass. Second, it was established for puma *Puma concolor*, whose digestive abilities differs from those of hyena. Nevertheless, both models H1 and H2 provided almost identical values of the relative % of consumed biomass, presented in Table S1.

Then the participation of given taxon in hyena's diet was calculated as:

$$P_i = \frac{BC_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n BC_i} \quad (\text{Eqn S3})$$

or

$$P_i = \frac{ABC_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n ABC_i} \quad (\text{Eqn S4})$$

respectively in models H1 and H2. The mean prey's isotopic value, either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{GlX}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, was calculated for each model as a weight balance of all prey taxa's mean isotopic value, according to the formula:

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{diet}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i \delta^x E_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i} \quad (\text{Eqn S5})$$

where $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{diet}}$ is the mean isotopic value of hyena prey (either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{GlX}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_i$ is the mean (arithmetic) isotopic value of an i^{th} taxon (either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{GlX}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, accordingly). The standard error of the mean diet's isotopic composition was calculated as propagation error, according to the formula:

$$SE_{\text{diet}} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i \sigma SE_i)^2} \quad (\text{Eqn S6})$$

where SE_{diet} is the standard error for a mean diet's $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{GlX}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ and SE_i is standard error of an i^{th} taxon's mean isotopic value (either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{GlX}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, accordingly). All calculations were performed in the MS Excel software; the spreadsheets are available in Tables S6–S7 (supplementary Excel file). The mean diet isotopic values are presented graphically in Fig. S4.

Table S1. Proportion of each taxon in hyena's mean diet in two models. The proportions represent the parameter P_i in our equations (Equations S3 and S4). Models H1 and H2 were adopted in our study after Krajcarz et al. (2025), and use the data presented therein.

Taxon	% biomass consumed	
	model H1	model H2
Reindeer	2.7	4.9
Bison/aurochs	2.5	2.6
Horse	1.4	1.7
Woolly rhino	33.0	31.9
Mammoth	52.1	49.9

Fig. S4. Perspektywiczna Cave hyena mean collagen isotopic values (+) and hyena's mean diet collagen isotopic values (×) in different mean diet models. **(A)** model H1 based on BC mean diet model of Krajcarz et al. (2025); **(B)** model H1 based on ABC mean diet model of Krajcarz et al. (2025). Gray dashed lines show the TP2 and TP3 levels as expected in the Chikaraishi et al.'s model (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011).

For wolf, we followed the prey structure of the Białowieża Forest wolves presented by Jędrzejewski et al. (2000). Due to several methods of the prey structure estimation presented therein, we adopted several models (called: model W1, model W2, and model W3). The percentage of prey according to these models is presented in [Table S2](#).

In model W1, we followed the average % of total biomass consumed by wolf packs for period 1985-1996, based on the analysis of feces (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000: Table 2). We averaged data presented for seasons. We utilized only data for species that were represented in our collagen collection, i.e.: red deer *Cervus elaphus*, roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*, European bison *Bison bonasus*, wild boar *Sus scrofa*, and

undetermined cervids. The included taxa summed up to over 97% of the total biomass consumed by wolves. We assumed that the group of undetermined cervids represented mostly red deer and roe deer in similar proportion as their proportion within the identified species (i.e., the red deer to roe deer proportion of 17.6 : 2.9). We summed the % of biomass for identified cervid species (red deer or roe deer) and portion of the % of biomass of undetermined cervids that was estimated to be the same species (red deer or roe deer, respectively). The mean prey's isotopic value, either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, and its standard error were calculated in the same way as for hyena (equations S5 and S6).

In model W2, we used prey structure based on number of kills recorded in 1985-1996 (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000: Table 3). Again, we utilized only data for species that were represented in our collagen collection, i.e.: red deer, roe deer, European bison, and wild boar. These taxa summed up to over 99% of the total number of kills by wolves. To correct for biomass, we multiplied the % of kills by prey average body mass. We followed the body masses by (Jędrzejewski et al. 2000) and for bison we used a body mass of 650 kg. The participation of a given taxon in wolf's diet was calculated as:

$$P_i = \frac{\%kill_i \cdot Bm_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \%kill_i \cdot Bm_i} \quad (\text{Eqn S7})$$

where $\%kill_i$ is the percentage of an i^{th} species in the wolf kills, and Bm_i is an i^{th} species average body mass in kg. The mean prey's isotopic value, either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, and its standard error were calculated in the same way as for the model W1 (Equations S5 and S6).

In model W3, we followed predation impact of wolf on red deer, roe deer, moose and wild boar, as recorded in 1991-1996 (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000: Table 4). Predation impact is an ecological parameter used to describe a consumptive effect that refers to the proportion of prey removed by a predator in a given period of time. The predation impact is calculated based on the number of wolf packs detected in each year, the size of their home ranges, the relative amount of prey species killed, the average killing rate of ungulates per wolf pack, and ungulate densities. Again, we utilized only data for species that were represented in our collagen collection, i.e.: red deer, roe deer, and wild boar. These taxa summed up to 100%, each species representing the average percentage of a species among wolf predation. Data for bison were not presented by Jędrzejewski et al. (2000) and thus bison was not included in the model W3. The mean prey's isotopic value, either $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, and its standard error were calculated in the same way as for the models W1 and W2 (Equations S5 and S6).

All calculations were performed in the MS Excel software; the spreadsheets are available in [Tables S3–S5](#) (supplementary Excel file). The mean diets' isotopic values are presented graphically in [Fig. S5](#).

Model W2 overestimates the importance of red deer in the wolf diet in relation to models W1 and W3. This model is vulnerable to trackability of kill spots; moreover, it does not include carrion eaten by wolves. We regard model W1 as the best representation of a nutrient flux from the prey to wolf.

Table S2. Proportion of each taxon's biomass in Białowieża Forest wolf diet in two models. The proportions represent the parameter P_i in our Equations S7 and proportions from the literature data. Models W1, W2 and W3 were adopted in our study after (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000) and use the data presented therein.

Taxon	% biomass consumed		
	model W1	model W2	model W3
red deer	69.9 (incl. 52.3*)	82.1	59.0
roe deer	11.5 (incl. 8.6*)	5.4	17.0
European bison	0.9	2.3	not incl.
wild boar	15.1	10.3	24.0

* species-related portion of the undetermined cervids

Fig. S5. Białowieża Forest wolf mean collagen isotopic values (+) and wolf's mean diet collagen isotopic values (×) in different mean diet models. **(A)** model W1 based on scat composition; **(B)** model W2 based on number of kills; **(C)** model W3 based on predation impact of wolf on the set of species (red deer, roe deer, moose, wild boar). Gray dashed lines show the TP2 and TP3 levels as expected in the Chikaraishi et al.'s model (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011).

TDF calculation

Our calculations followed the method presented by Krajcarz et al. (2025). First, we obtained the average isotopic composition of Glx and Phe of the carnivore and those of its mean diet, separately for each mean diet model. The predator's average composition is simply an average of all its samples' $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values, respectively. Its standard error (SE) propagates according to usual error propagation rules as:

$$SE_{\text{taxon}} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{SD_i}{n}\right)^2} \quad (\text{Eqn S8})$$

where SE_{taxon} is the standard error for the given taxon, i is the i^{th} measured sample within the taxon, n is a number of samples, and SD_i is the standard deviation of the i^{th} sample triplicate analysis. The same formula was used for SE of each prey taxon.

The mean isotopic value of the carnivore's diet was calculated following the methodology of Krajcarz et al. (2025). It was calculated as a weight balance of all prey taxa's mean isotopic values (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$), according to the formula:

$$\delta^{15}N_{diet} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m P_j \delta^{15}N_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m P_j} \quad (\text{Eqn S9})$$

where $\delta^{15}N_{diet}$ is the mean isotopic value of the carnivore's diet (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$), m is a number of prey taxa in the diet, P_j is the proportion of a j^{th} taxon in the carnivore's diet, and $\delta^{15}N_j$ is the mean (arithmetic) isotopic value of a j^{th} taxon (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$, respectively). The proportion of each prey taxon in the carnivore's diet is explained in the section **Diet composition** in the main text and details are presented in the **Supplementary Text: Mean diet estimation** section. The standard error of the mean diet's isotopic composition was calculated as propagation error, according to the formula:

$$SE_{diet} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^m (\sigma_j)^{-2}}} \quad (\text{Eqn S10})$$

where SE_{diet} is the standard error for a mean prey and σ_j is standard error of a j^{th} taxon's mean isotopic value (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$, respectively).

Glu and Phe individual TDFs were then calculated as differences between carnivore's mean isotopic value and its modeled mean diet isotopic values (independently for $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ and for $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$), according to the formula:

$$\Delta^{15}N_{carnivore} = \delta^{15}N_{carnivore} - \delta^{15}N_{diet} \quad (\text{Eqn S11})$$

The standard errors of these individual Glx or Phe TDFs were calculated as a propagation errors for the difference of the mean carnivore's isotopic value and the mean diet's isotopic value (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$), according to the formula:

$$SE_{\Delta} = \sqrt{SE_{carnivore}^2 + SE_{diet}^2} \quad (\text{Eqn S12})$$

where SE_{Δ} is standard error for $\Delta^{15}N_{carnivore}$ (either $\delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ or $\delta^{15}N_{Phe}$, respectively). Finally, the $TDF_{Glx-Phe}$ was simply calculated as a difference between Glx $\Delta^{15}N$ and Phe $\Delta^{15}N$ for a given carnivore, according to the formula:

$$TDF_{Glx-Phe} = \Delta^{15}N_{Glx} - \Delta^{15}N_{Phe} \quad (\text{Eqn S13})$$

The standard error for $TDF_{Glx-Phe}$ was calculated as error propagation, according to the formula:

$$SE_{TDF_{Glx-Phe}} = \sqrt{SE_{\Delta_{Glx}}^2 + SE_{\Delta_{Phe}}^2} \quad (\text{Eqn S14})$$

TP equation

Our TP equation follows the concept of (Chikaraishi et al., 2009) and a general model as follows:

$$TP = \frac{\delta^{15}N_{Glx(sample)} - \delta^{15}N_{Phe(sample)} - (\delta^{15}N_{Glx(baseline)} - \delta^{15}N_{Phe(baseline)})}{TDF_{Glx-Phe}} + B \quad (\text{Eqn S15})$$

where $\delta^{15}N_{Glx(sample)}$ and $\delta^{15}N_{Phe(sample)}$ are the $\delta^{15}N$ values measured in a sample of interest, the $\delta^{15}N_{Glx(baseline)} - \delta^{15}N_{Phe(baseline)}$ is the difference between the $\delta^{15}N$ values in the baseline level (i.e., the β value), and B is the

TP of the baseline level. Originally (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011), this equation assumed that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ difference in the then-selected baseline level, i.e., plants, was constant (and called the β value). Knowing that this assumption is no longer valid and that the TDF between plant and collagen likely differs from the TDF between collagen and collagen (see section [Problem of the \$\beta\$ value variability](#) in the main text), we selected herbivores as a more suitable baseline for collagen-to-collagen studies. We further assumed that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ difference in herbivores may be non-constant, however, it can be approximated by a linear function $y = ax + b$, in particular the Equation 3 presented in the main text:

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herb})} = a_h \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herb})} + b_h \quad (\text{Eqn 3})$$

where a_h and b_h are slope and intercept of the herbivore regression. We transformed the Equation S15 to:

$$TP = \frac{(\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})}) - (\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})})}{TDF_{\text{Glx-Phe}}} + 2 \quad (\text{Eqn S16})$$

where $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})}$ replaced the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{baseline})}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{baseline})}$ (to indicate that they represent a herbivore baseline) and B was replaced by 2, to anchor the formula at the herbivore level, i.e., at $TP = 2$. In contrast to the Equation S15, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})}$ represent here the isotopic values of a point within the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ isospace rather than an arbitrary and constant difference. Graphical representation is presented in [Fig. S6](#). The $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore}), \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})}$ point represents the starting point in a trophic chain (i.e., the herbivore collagen isotopic value; an open circle in [Fig. S6](#)) that could lead to the sample datapoint (i.e., the consumer's collagen isotopic value, would it be the same herbivore or a carnivore; the black dot in [Fig. S6](#)) if the accepted TDF_{Glx} and TDF_{Phe} are applied. The vertical and horizontal distances between both points, called H and L , are thus the multiplications of TDF_{Glx} and TDF_{Phe} values, keeping the proportion between both TDFs.

Fig. S6. Graphical depiction of the parameters used in the TP level calculation. The TP of a sample datapoint (black dot), according to the Equation 4 in the main text, is the quotient of the difference $H - L$ and the $TDF_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ (or the $TDF_{\text{Glx}} - TDF_{\text{Phe}}$ difference). H and L are the distances between the sample datapoint (black dot) and a theoretical herbivore datapoint (open circle) that serve as a starting point for this trophic chain. The proportion between H and L equals the proportion between TDF_{Glx} and TDF_{Phe} . In the case of a perfect herbivore sample (i.e., situated on the regression line), the H and L equal 0. This way of TP calculation provides the trophic level above the baseline, which in this case is $TP = 2$ herbivore level, therefore the result must be increased by +2.

All these assumptions gave us a series of four equations:

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})} = a_h \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})} + b_h \quad (\text{Eqn 3})$$

$$H = \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})} \quad (\text{Eqn S17})$$

$$L = \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})} \quad (\text{Eqn S18})$$

$$\frac{H}{L} = \frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}} \quad (\text{Eqn S19})$$

where unknown are: H , L , $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})}$, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})}$; and only the last two unknowns are important for the Equation S16. The solution of this series of equations gave:

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{herbivore})} = \frac{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{sample})} + b_h}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}}}{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} - a_h}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}}} \quad (\text{Eqn S20})$$

and

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{herbivore})} = \frac{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{sample})} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{sample})} - \frac{b_h}{a_h}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} - \frac{1}{a_h}}}{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}}}} \quad (\text{Eqn S21}).$$

The respective substitution in Equation S16 provided the final equation for the TP, i.e., the Equation 4 presented in the main text:

$$TP = \frac{\left(\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \frac{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - \frac{b_h}{a_h}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}}}}{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} - \frac{1}{a_h}}} \right) - \left(\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - \frac{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} + b_h}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}}}{\frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}} - a_h}} \right)}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} - \text{Phe}} + 2 \quad (\text{Eqn 4})$$

where $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}(\text{sample})}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}(\text{sample})}$ were replaced by $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ for readability.

Supplementary tables (separate Excel file) for

New model for estimating trophic level in mammalian carnivores based on bone collagen individual amino acids nitrogen stable isotopes

Table S3:

Wolf TDF (model W1). The table contains calculations of the TDF based on the Białowieża Forest dataset. The wolf mean diet is based on scat content, adopted from Table 2 in Jędrzejewski et al. (2000).

Table S4:

Wolf TDF (model W2). The table contains calculations of the TDF based on the Białowieża Forest dataset. The wolf mean diet is based on number of kills, adopted from Table 3 in Jędrzejewski et al. (2000).

Table S5:

Wolf TDF (model W3). The table contains calculations of the TDF based on the Białowieża Forest dataset. The wolf mean diet is based on wolf predation on the set of species (red deer, roe deer, moose, wild boar), adopted from Table 4 in Jędrzejewski et al. (2000).

Table S6:

Hyena TDF (model H1). The table contains calculations of the TDF based on the Perspektywiczna Cave hyena den dataset. The hyena mean diet is based on NISP of ZooMS-identified digested bones transformed into biomass – data adopted from the BC model in Krajcarz et al. (2025).

Table S7:

Hyena TDF (model H2). The table contains calculations of the TDF based on the Perspektywiczna Cave hyena den dataset. The hyena mean diet is based on NISP of ZooMS-identified digested bones transformed into biomass – data adopted from the ABC model in Krajcarz et al. (2025).

Table S8:

Exemplary TP estimation. Calculation of the TP for exemplary dataset of the Buran-Kaya III site (data from (Drucker et al., 2017)) based on our average TDF above the herbivore baseline. Comparison with the traditional TP estimation based on (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011) is also presented.

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